

Consumptive Behaviour in Metrosexual

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the description of metrosexual behaviour, consumptive behaviour, and factors that influence consumptive behaviour in metrosexual men. The approach used in this research is a qualitative approach in the form of a case study with the research subject a 23-year-old metrosexual man who lives in the city of Bandung. In this interview using the guided interview method and with non-participant observation. Based on the research results obtained, it can be concluded that in general it can be said that the subject undergoes metrosexual behaviour, this is reflected in the subject's extravagant behaviour, maintaining appearance to build a new image, excessive shopping, doing body care. Consumptive behaviour carried out by the subject as a metrosexual man can be seen from the subject's large amount of income, always using the latest gadgets, prioritising fulfilling wants over needs, buying new items every month, and clubbing. The factors that cause the subject to carry out consumptive behaviour can be concluded that the subject wants to maintain the good name of the parents, the pleasure after shopping, and the negative opinions of others encourage the subject to be more all out.

Keywords: Consumptive behaviour, Male, Metrosexual.

1. Introduction

Men are generally characterised by masculine traits that are more active, competitive, aggressive, dominant, independent and confident. Females, on the other hand, are considered to be more of a feminine character who is sweet, neat, calm, emotional, expressive, sensitive and tactical. Men are always associated with independence while women are associated with dependence. That is what distinguishes men from women (Handayani & Ardhan, 2004). There is also the metrosexual phenomenon, where it is not only women who have the nature to discipline themselves in body care, but also men. Iconisation through world-renowned celebrities such as soccer player David Beckham, who appears well-dressed, has become a driving force for men around the world to emulate him. A new type of urban male worships a hedonistic lifestyle, looking trendy and always following the latest trends. Perfumes, clothes, accessories from famous brands previously only used by women, are now found on metrosexual men (Mulyana, 2014).

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Based on the results of the interview, it is known that the subject is a man who lives in Bandung and works as an admin manager at a company in Buah Batu city. The subject is the first of three children, the subject's family lives in Jakarta, the subject's father is a captain and the subject's mother is a housewife. The subject is a man who pays more attention to his appearance than men in general, and also does periodic maintenance for his body such as scrubbing once every two weeks and facials which are done once a week regularly. The subject is also very concerned about the fashion he uses and has his own brand of fashion choices. The subject also often goes clubbing with his friends This shows that the subject belongs to the category of metrosexual men.

2. Research Method

2. 1 Research Approach

The type of research approach in this study is a case study. Raco said (2010), a case study is part of a qualitative method that wants to explore a particular case in more depth by involving the collection of multiple sources of information.

2. 2 Research Subject

The subject of this research is a 23-year-old metrosexual man who lives in the city of Bandung.

2. 3 Data Collection Methods

2. 3. 1 This research uses a type of guided interview, where there are guidelines or guidelines that have been designed and arranged systematically and in writing.

2. 3. 2 This research uses a type of non-participant observation where the researcher is not involved and only as an independent observer. Data collection with non-participant observation will not get in-depth data, with the aim that the subjects observed are more realistic and natural and the researcher can record all the things the subject does.

2. 4 Research Triangulation

Triangulation in this study used is data triangulation, method triangulation, researcher triangulation and theory triangulation.

3. Results and Discussion

The characteristics of metrosexual men are as men who live and stay in big cities, come from wealthy circles, have a hedonistic lifestyle, follow fashion developments, pay attention to appearance and do body care. It is also explained that metrosexual men usually come from circles with large economic income, therefore the amount of material spent to support their consumptive behaviour is not a problem. The subject feels that he is very wasteful when he is bored, the subject always wants to spend money and shop, even though this is not the subject's need. This is in accordance with what is stated by Lina and Rasyid (1997), consumptive behaviour tends to be wasteful by spending an item not solely because of need, but has another basic orientation, not looking at the usefulness and benefits of the item, but rather driven by the desire to spend without clear limits and goals.

According to Sumartono (2002), indicators of consumptive behaviour are to maintain appearance and prestige, just to maintain a status symbol, and to create confidence with expensive products, and to try more than two similar products. The subject buys not because of necessity but because of his desires.

Setiadi (2011) states that a person's social status makes a person's role will maintain and maintain his status with his behaviour and social actions. Likewise, the status possessed by his parents "the social stratification of parents will affect the socialisation of their children". In this case the environment also greatly influences the subject to carry out consumptive behaviour, such as if there is someone who underestimates the subject, then the subject will be more all out.

As stated by Klass & Hedge (in Ghufon & Risnawati, 2010), self-esteem is a process of judgement that individuals make and maintain about themselves. The assessment process comes from the individual's interaction with the environment and involves aspects such as acceptance, treatment and appreciation of others towards him.

As stated by Peterson & Seligman (2004), individuals with disciplinary character strengths or persistence are individuals who always complete everything they have started, despite facing various challenges.

In addition, the subject also feels a special pleasure when the subject is shopping, the subject always feels satisfied with whatever item he buys, because it can be said that the subject is someone who is quite selective in choosing goods. This is an impetus for the subject to continue to engage in consumptive behaviour. This is also explained by Suyanto (2013) who states that consumers buy consumer goods to seek pleasure. Pleasure here usually also takes advantage of free time to find pleasure so that someone will behave consumptively. Consumers carry out consumption activities with the aim of fulfilling their life

needs. Therefore, to make this happen, consumers will buy whatever goods and services they want so that they will get maximum satisfaction (Waluyo, Suwardi, Agung, and Tri, 2008). According to Sunyoto (2014), this case is included in the internal factors that come from themselves, namely motivation. The motivation referred to here is an overall drive and individual desire directed at the goal of obtaining satisfaction.

4. Conclusions

Based on the results of the analysis, several things can be concluded, namely: In general, it can be said that the subject lives the behaviour of a metrosexual man, this is reflected in the subject's wasteful behaviour, maintaining appearance to build a new image, excessive shopping, doing body care. Consumptive behaviour carried out by the subject as a metrosexual man is seen from the subject's large amount of income, always wearing the latest gadgets, prioritising fulfilling wants rather than needs, buying new items every month, and clubbing and the factors that cause the subject to carry out consumptive behaviour can be concluded that there are external and internal factors, the external factor is that the subject wants to maintain the good name of the parents because of the father's work status, and the negative opinions of others become the driving force for the subject to be more all out, also the internal factor is the pleasure after shopping.

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